

MANAGE PRODUCT QUALITY IN ENTERPRISES CONTENT

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Abstract: To increase the quality of the product, to ensure the production of products that are most suitable for the existing and future needs, to increase the technical level and quality of the product to the level of the best foreign samples, to provide them with resources and to determine the economically acceptable tasks for increasing the quality of the product from the point of view of consumer requests. Product quality management is understood as the activities carried out to create, use, consume, determine, ensure, and maintain the required level of product quality.

Keywords: quality, product, planning, mechanism, conformity, certificate, resource, standard, the international standard, normative document, technical documents, facility, system.

The product quality management mechanism consists of a set of interrelated management objects and entities, management principles, methods, and functions used at different stages of the product life cycle, and different levels of quality management. In this case, indicators and descriptions of product quality, factors and conditions affecting their level, as well as processes of formation of product quality at different stages of the product life cycle are the direct objects of management. Various management bodies and individual persons working at different levels and performing quality management functions following generally accepted principles and methods of management are management subjects. Product quality management refers to the actions taken to establish, ensure, and maintain the required level of product quality during product creation, use, or consumption [1].

Among the general subsystems of the product quality control mechanism, it is necessary to include forecasting and planning of the technical level and quality of the product, control of product quality in direct production, product quality control, accounting and analysis of changes in quality levels, incentives and responsibility for quality. Special subsystems of the product quality control mechanism include standardization, product testing, prevention of defects in production, attestation, and certification. It includes small systems that provide a mechanism for product quality control information supply, material, and technical supply, metrological supply, personnel supply, organizational supply, technological supply, and financial supply consisting of small systems [2].

Among the main functions of product quality management, first of all, assessment of market needs, technical level and quality of products, planning to increase product quality, standardization and standardization of product quality requirements, product development and production, technological preparation of production, raw materials, materials, semi-finished products and the organization of mutual relations on product quality between suppliers of components, enterprises manufacturing products and their consumers, ensuring the stability of the planned quality level at all stages of the product life cycle, controlling and testing product quality, preventing inconsistencies in production, products, technological processes, certification of workplaces, executors and others in production, certification of products, works, services, quality and production systems, incentives and responsibility for the level of quality achieved, product quality internal production includes accounting and reporting, technical and economic analysis of product quality changes, ensuring product quality management, special training and professional development of personnel [3].

Product quality planning is defined as the determination of tasks based on the production of products with the value of quality indicators at the required level at the same time or within a specified period. Quality improvement planning must be based on a scientifically based assessment of domestic and foreign market needs [4]. To properly justify quality improvement plans, it is necessary to use information about the results of product use and summarize and analyze information about the

actual level of product quality. The subject of product quality planning is various indicators that reflect both the individual properties of the product and the various descriptions of the quality management system and processes. These indicators are reflected in specific assignments for product quality improvement, scientific research and experimental construction work, standardization, and metrological supply, the introduction of a quality management system, technical development of the enterprise, and personnel training plans [5].

The most important principles of planning to improve product quality are the scientific development of plans, taking into account the latest advances in science and technology, the requirements of standards in the future, market needs (both existing and future), comprehensiveness, all aspects of the enterprise's activities in quality plans, and the creation of new technology. , envisages the introduction of standards, increase of production volume, and harmonization. The complexity of the planning means that it is important that the tasks for improving the quality of the final product are coordinated with the plans for improving the quality of the products supplied by business partners who supply the enterprise with raw materials, materials, semi-finished products, components, spare parts and other components of the final product.

The main tasks of planning to improve product quality are to ensure the production of products that are most suitable for the current and future needs of the market, to increase the technical level and quality of products to the level of the best domestic and foreign samples, to provide them with resources and to increase the quality of products from the point of view of consumer requests. determining optimal tasks, improving the structure of the produced product by optimizing the range of its type sizes, increasing the production of certified products, improving the reliability, long-term durability, safety, and economy of some consumer properties of the previously produced product, morally obsolete and unable to withstand competition timely reduction of product production or withdrawal from production, strict compliance with the requirements of standards, technical conditions, and other regulatory and technical

documents It consists in ensuring safety, timely introduction of newly developed standards and revision of outdated ones, development and implementation of specific measures that ensure the achievement of the specified level of quality, increasing the economic efficiency of production and the use of products with improved quality [6]. Quality improvement planning needs to be implemented at different levels of management and different stages of the product life cycle, including design, production, and use. Quality improvement plans must be provided with the necessary materials, and financial and labor resources, and the indicators and activities planned for quality improvement must be carefully based on cost-effectiveness calculations [7].

Planning to improve product quality in enterprises is the priority it is necessary to study the current and prospective requirements for the product in detail, analyze the opinions of consumers about the condition of the product during use, and develop contracts with customers. Quality improvement plans should also be based on the results of product certification, advanced requirements of current standards and technical conditions, results of scientific research, patent materials, licenses, scientific and technical information, and consumer requirements [8]. Large companies with their scientific research department carry out not only current but also prospective planning and forecasting of the quality of their products. Actual indicators of production efficiency and quality, regulatory and technical documents, patents, scientific developments, and assessment materials by experts serve as a source of information. Depending on the type of product and the tasks ahead, different methods of evaluation can be used, such as modeling, expert evaluation, mathematical statistics, extrapolation, etc [9].

Planned changes in product cost, profit, production profitability, number of employees, wages, and capital investment amounts related to the implementation of measures to improve product quality must be confirmed by appropriate calculations. Planned tasks and obligations for product quality improvement should be coordinated with other departments of enterprise plans, as well as provided with

necessary materials, labor, and financial resources [10]. As independent areas of planning to improve product quality in the enterprise, planning product quality within the company, planning the introduction of a quality management system in the enterprise, planning the provision of personnel to increase product quality, planning the losses that the enterprise may suffer as a result of internal and external inconsistencies, planning product quality in contracts and contracts, Next In 2010, one of the important areas of planning to improve the quality of products in the enterprise is the planning of preparation for certification of manufactured goods, quality system and production. Enterprises that produce final products must provide various assistance to enterprises that supply raw materials and others to improve the quality of their products. Such forms of support, as well as the costs of providing it, should be the subject of planning to improve product quality in the enterprise [11].

complement the planning of the product quality improvement in the enterprises themselves with the planning within the productions. In this case, it is possible to use generalizing, unified and complex indicators of quality, which can be classified taking into account the specific characteristics of the types and levels of planning. The plans of the main workshops should include tasks to improve the quality of parts, details, and assembly units through the production process of this workshop [12]. This may include the tasks of increasing the accuracy and cleanliness of processing, expanding the production of details covered with special types of coatings and mastering the production of new products. For assembly shops, it is desirable to plan product quality indicators set at the enterprise level, as well as indicators to reduce the loss of non-conformance and complaints, as well as delivery at the first presentation of the product itself. The last two indicators can also be used for machining shops, sections, and brigades. These shops should plan to reduce the number of parts and joints sent back from the shops that use their product. It is appropriate to plan both activities and indicators that are necessary to ensure the high quality of products in the main production shops for each workshop of auxiliary production. For example, for a repair shop, the most important indicator may be the percentage of the total volume of equipment, repaired machines, and machines that have

reached the specified level of technical accuracy after repair. Along with product quality improvement plans for workshops and sections, it is advisable to develop corresponding plans for functional departments and services. The tasks of developing new types of products, improving the quality of products that need to be modernized, and increasing the level of aggregation and unification can be included in the plan of design departments. For technical services, it is appropriate to plan activities that meet the profile of these units [13]. For example, the plan of the chief technologist's department should include the tasks of introducing modern technological processes, eliminating inconsistencies, and equipping production with various devices. The object of planning within the firm can be the quality of product preparation and the quality of work [14]. In shops, this is the percentage of products accepted in the first delivery itself, the reduction of damage caused by scrap, claims, and the reduction of items returned from shops. In design, construction, and technological services - the percentage of technical documents that are returned for processing and submission at the first submission of documents. In the technical control department - reduction of the number of complaints, state of control measuring equipment, etc. can be [15]. Indicators of quality improvement must be connected with other indicators of evaluation of the activity of departments within the enterprise, as well as the obligations of employees and their incentive system.

References:

1. Juraboevich B. N. Products in Manufacturing Enterprises the Essence of Quality Management //International Journal of Development and Public Policy. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 117-118.
2. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бердимуродов Г. Т., Бадалов У. Н. СИФАТЛИ МАХСУЛОТ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИЛИШИДА СИНОВ ВА ЎЛЧОВЛАРНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //ЎТМОЙ FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 101-106.
3. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МАХСУЛОТЛАР СИФАТИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ //Academic research in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 38-45.
4. Juraboyevich B. N. et al. Development Of Metrology And The Role And Importance Of Metrological Supply In Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 136-139.
5. Juraboyevich B. N., Son B. O. N. THE ROLE OF QUALITY PRODUCTION IN ENTERPRISES //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 9. – №. 10. – С. 644-647.
6. Jo'raboevich B. N. QUALITY EXPORT PRODUCTS IN ENTERPRISES GENERAL AND SPECIAL IN

- PRODUCTION IMPORTANCE OF REGULATIONS //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 1-7.
7. Jo'raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SINOVA VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDA KOMPETENTLIGINI XALQARO DARAJADA OSHIRISH OMILLARI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 128-131.
 8. Бадалов Н. Ж., Икромов Д. И., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА ЎЛЧАШЛАР, СИНОВЛАР ВА ТАҲЛИЛЛАРНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК АХАМИЯТИ //Международная конференция академических наук. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 15. – С. 11-17.
 9. Jo'raboyevich B. N. ROLE OF COMPARISON, CALIBRATION AND METROLOGICAL CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 168-175.
 10. Jo'raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SIFAT MENEJMENT TIZIMINING-SINOVA VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDAGI O'RNINI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 67-71.
 11. BADALOV N. J., RUSTAMOV N. T. THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES THAT HAVE IMPLEMENTED A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 46-55.
 12. Jo'raboevich B. N., Abduraxmonovich S. H. M. KORXONALARDA O'LGAN VOSITALARNI SINOVDA O'TKAZISHDA METROLOGIK XIZMATINING O'RNINI //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 701-704.
 13. BADALOV N. J. O. R. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES WITH A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 146-156.
 14. O'g B. O. N. et al. The role of quality management system in increasing product quality in enterprises //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 228-233.
 15. BADALOV U. N. O. THE IMPORTANCE OF TESTING LABORATORIES AND THEIR ACCREDITATION //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 163-169.